

The background of the entire page is a photograph of a vineyard at dusk or dawn, with warm, golden light filtering through the leaves. Overlaid on this are several sets of thin, curved, parallel lines in a dark purple color, creating a sense of motion and precision. A large, solid purple rectangular area is positioned in the upper right, containing the main title text.

Precision viticulture for a changing climate

White Paper

MONTEVITIS
Together for the mitigation of climate change's impact on viticulture

TOGETHER FOR THE MITIGATION OF CLIMATE CHANGE'S IMPACT ON VITICULTURE

AUTHORS

ANNARITA BALINGIT
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE (UNIFI)
Italy

NICCOLÒ BARTOLONI
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE (UNIFI)
Italy

CAMILLA DIBARI
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE (UNIFI)
Italy

LUISA LEOLINI
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE (UNIFI)
Italy

KRISTINA HEILEMANN
LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY (LIST)
Luxembourg

DANIEL MOLITOR
LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY (LIST)
Luxembourg

KRUNA RATKOVIĆ
UNIVERZITET DONJA GORICA (UDG)
Montenegro

NATAŠA KOVAČ
UNIVERZITET DONJA GORICA (UDG)
Montenegro

MARKO SIMEUNOVIĆ
UNIVERZITET DONJA GORICA (UDG)
Montenegro

SANJA RADONJIĆ
UNIVERZITET DONJA GORICA (UDG)
Montenegro

ANTÓNIO CARLOS PINHEIRO FERNANDES
UNIVERSIDADE DE TRÁS-OS-MONTES E ALTO
DOURO (UTAD)
Portugal

HELDER FRAGA
UNIVERSIDADE DE TRÁS-OS-MONTES E ALTO
DOURO (UTAD)
Portugal

JOÃO CARLOS ANDRADE DOS SANTOS
UNIVERSIDADE DE TRÁS-OS-MONTES E ALTO
DOURO (UTAD)
Portugal

CHRISTOPH MENZ
POTSDAM-INSTITUT FÜR
KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG E.V. (PIK)
Germany

CONSORTIUM

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Coordination and Support action under the Grant Agreement n° 101059461.

INDEX

Pages

List of Figures

IV

Executive Summary

V

1. The MONTEVITIS project

07

2. Wine sector in Montenegro

11

2.1 Viticultural landscape and wine production in Montenegro

13

2.2 Socio-economic impacts and future perspectives

17

3. Effects of climate change on Montenegrin viticulture

19

3.1 Climate change in Montenegro

21

3.2 Climate change impacts on Montenegrin viticulture

26

4. Precision farming

31

4.1 Remote sensing

33

4.2 Proximal sensing

34

4.3 Decision support system

35

5. Adaptation and mitigation measures

39

5.1 Adaptation measures

41

5.2 Mitigation measures

46

5.3 Case studies in Montenegro

49

6. Future perspectives for viticulture in Montenegro: knowledge gaps and future challenges

51

6.1 New perspective in viticulture in Montenegro: main research findings and opportunities

53

6.2 Stakeholder collaboration: long-term networks for data sharing

55

6.3 Capacity-building initiatives

56

7. Digital atlas

57

8. Conclusions

61

Bibliography

65

LIST OF FIGURES

Pages

Figure 1: Montenegro viticulture regions	13
Figure 2: Surface structure of red wine varieties in Montenegro	16
Figure 3: Spatial distribution of projected temperature and precipitation changes.	22
Figure 4: Growing season average temperature	25
Figure 5: Global circulation model experiments for the Winkler index	26
Figure 6: Projected changes in the day of year (DOY) of key phenological stages	28
Figure 7: Witnessed changes in viticulture and winemaking sector	29
Figure 8: Witnessed changes in grapevine phenology	30
Figure 9: Use of drones for remote sensing and precision monitoring in vineyards	34
Figure 10: Proximal sensor monitoring vineyard conditions	35
Figure 11: Decision support system (DSS)	36
Figure 12: DSS map of minimum temperature distribution	36
Figure 13: DSS view of vineyard sensor data	37
Figure 14: Result of the questionnaire after the workshop	41
Figure 15: Kaolin on grapes of defoliated vines	42
Figure 16: Cover crops growing between vine rows	44
Figure 17: Grapes of Sauvignier gris	45
Figure 18: Biochar application	47
Figure 19: Volume of water for optimisation of pesticide treatments in a vineyard.	47
Figure 20: Agrovoltaic system	48
Figure 21: Research on viti-voltaic systems at WBI Freiburg in Germany	48
Figure 22: Digital atlas of Montenegro as an integral part of DSS Montevitis platform	59

TABLES

Table 1: Evaluation of various climate indices for 4 different regions of Montenegro	23
---	----

The background of the page is a photograph of a vineyard. The vines are trained on a trellis system, and the leaves are showing signs of autumn, with some turning yellow and orange. The lighting is soft, suggesting a late afternoon or early morning setting. Overlaid on the left side of the image are several decorative, wavy, purple lines that create a sense of movement and depth. A dark purple rectangular box is positioned in the upper left quadrant, containing the text 'Executive Summary' in white.

Executive Summary

Viticulture in Montenegro is a sector of major economic, social, and cultural significance. It combines a long-standing heritage with an expanding role in international markets. Yet, the sector is increasingly vulnerable to climate change: rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and more frequent extreme events directly affect productivity and quality, putting long-term sustainability at risk.

The MONTEVITIS project was established to address these challenges by reinforcing Montenegro's research and innovation capacity and promoting the adoption of advanced scientific and technological solutions. Through collaboration between universities, research centres, wineries, and institutions, it develops modelling tools, IoT-based monitoring systems, precision agriculture practices, and training activities, while supporting the valorisation of indigenous grape varieties and Montenegro's integration into the European research area.

This document highlights the dual reality of the sector: its socio-economic importance for rural communities and national development, and its exposure to risks under projected climate scenarios. Within this framework, strategies are considered at two complementary levels. One dimension focuses on helping vineyards cope with changing environmental conditions, safeguarding yield and quality despite increasing climatic variability. This requires the implementation of adaptation strategies, which consist of adjustments to the vineyard management, such as pruning, irrigation, or the choice of appropriate varieties and rootstocks, all aimed at maintaining resilience and productivity. At the same time, it is essential to reduce the sector's contribution to climate change while improving environmental performance. This involves mitigation strategies that lower greenhouse gas emissions, strengthen soil and canopy management, and foster carbon sequestration, thereby aligning viticulture with sustainability and climate objectives.

Through these combined actions, MONTEVITIS is expected to enhance resilience and safeguard genetic and viticultural heritage. Concurrently, there is an expectation that they will enhance international competitiveness and align Montenegro more closely with European priorities on sustainability and ecological transition, ensuring that climate change challenges are addressed through innovation and sustainable growth.

1 The MONTEVITIS Project

The MONTEVITIS project

Viticulture is highly sensitive to climatic conditions, making it particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change. Changing climate patterns, increased temperature extremes, and unpredictable weather variations significantly impact grapevine growth, yield, and wine quality. To ensure the long-term sustainability and resilience of this sector, proactive adaptation and mitigation strategies are essential, driven by real-time monitoring and data-informed decision-making. The Mediterranean and Western Balkan regions, including Montenegro, face unique challenges due to the lack of systematic monitoring and science-based decision-making tools for climate adaptation in vineyards. Montenegro lacks sufficient research capabilities and technological tools to effectively assess, adapt to, and mitigate climate-related impacts on viticulture. Without targeted intervention, including climate adaptation strategies, the wine industry, an essential part of Montenegro's economy, risks declining productivity, reduced quality, and loss of competitiveness in global markets.

The MONTEVITIS project enhances research and innovation capacities in Montenegro's viticulture sector by leveraging expertise from leading European institutions. Its primary objectives include adapting analytical and modelling tools to assess the regional effects of climate change on viticulture. This involves understanding how changing climatic conditions influence grapevine physiological processes, yield, ripening, and wine quality across different grape varieties. Additionally, the project aims to introduce smart farming technologies, such as IoT-based monitoring systems and decision-support tools, to optimise vineyard management practices and enhance adaptation strategies. Knowledge exchange and capacity building strengthen and enhance the research and innovation ecosystem in Montenegro by fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and policymakers. The project ensures Montenegro's continued participation in European research initiatives, increasing its competitiveness in climate-smart viticulture. Additionally, MONTEVITIS increases the Research and Development (R&D) capacities of the University of Donja Gorica (UDG), enabling it to expand its expertise in viticulture, climate science, and precision agriculture while fostering interdisciplinary research collaborations.

Through its collaborative research, MONTEVITIS generates critical data and develops technological solutions to enhance the resilience and sustainability of Montenegro's viticulture sector. Key outcomes include the creation of a consolidated database integrating climate data, grapevine growth parameters, and mini Internet of Things (IoT)-based vineyard monitoring data, providing a comprehensive foundation for climate impact analysis. The project also focuses on developing mathematical models tailored for both local and international grape varieties, enabling more accurate impact assessments and adaptation strategies. Precision viticulture technologies, including mini-IoT pilot installations in vineyards, are being implemented to support data-driven decision-making. Additionally, the project contributes to scientific advancements through the publication of research outputs on climate change adaptation in viticulture. Capacity building is a critical component, with workshops, staff exchanges, and thematic events fostering knowledge transfer between European and Montenegrin stakeholders. Finally, the establishment of a Decision Support System (DSS) aids viticulturists in real-time vineyard management and climate adaptation planning.

2 Wine sector in Montenegro

Wine sector in Montenegro

SUMMARY

Viticulture in Montenegro represents a unique intersection of history, geography, and economic development. Rooted in centuries-old traditions and shaped by diverse terroirs, the wine sector plays a significant role in rural livelihoods, national identity, and export-oriented agriculture. Autochthonous grape varieties, combined with emerging boutique production and strong tourism links, provide a solid foundation for differentiation on international markets. At the same time, the sector is increasingly exposed to structural and external pressures, including climate variability, regulatory changes, and market competition. Understanding the current organisation, production patterns, and socio-economic relevance of Montenegrin viticulture is therefore essential for identifying pathways toward resilience, innovation, and long-term sustainability.

2.1. VITICULTURAL LANDSCAPE AND WINE PRODUCTION IN MONTENEGRO

Montenegro's viticulture holds a profound historical and cultural significance, tracing its origins back to the Illyrian and Roman eras around 2000 BC. Throughout centuries, viticulture has remained an enduring element of the country's agricultural identity, evolving from small-scale traditional practices into a structured and economically vital sector. While the legacy of ancient grape cultivation is preserved in oral traditions and archaeological evidence, the modernisation of viticulture in Montenegro has gained momentum in recent decades, shaped by state-supported zoning, private sector investments, and scientific research initiatives. The 2017 vineyard zoning study defined four key viticultural regions in the country: Skadar Lake Basin, Coastal Region, Northern Montenegro, and Nudo, each featuring a diverse set of subregions and microclimatic conditions that influence grapevine behaviour, varietal expression, and final wine profiles (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Montenegro Viticulture Regions.

The Skadar Lake Basin is Montenegro's primary and most productive wine region, encompassing subregions such as Podgorica, Crmnica, Rijeka, Bjelopavlići, Katun, Kuči, and Piperi. This area alone accounts for 99.25% of Montenegro's registered vineyard surface (2,561.33ha) and 96.81% of all registered grape and wine producers.

It benefits from a warm Mediterranean climate with long, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The presence of Lake Skadar creates a unique moderating effect on temperature extremes, reducing the likelihood of spring frosts and enhancing the terroir's potential for producing high-quality, full-bodied red wines. This is further supported by well-drained alluvial and karst soils that contribute to rich phenolic development in grapes.

Over the past two decades, however, climate trends such as prolonged heatwaves and irregular rainfall have required the introduction of improved irrigation systems and climate-smart viticultural practices.

The Coastal Wine-Growing Region, encompassing subregions such as Boka Kotorska, Budva, Bar, and Ulcinj, offers an equally Mediterranean profile but with distinct maritime influences from the Adriatic Sea. Although it constitutes only 0.68% of the total vineyard area and 1.09% of producers, this region offers great enotourism potential due to its popularity with visitors. The mild winters and extended growing season make it suitable for cultivating aromatic whites and balanced reds, though viticulture here faces additional challenges from abrupt temperature shifts, strong coastal winds, and variable precipitation.

Northern Montenegro, including Nikšić, Bijelo Polje, Šćepan Polje, and Dragalj, represents a nascent but promising wine territory. With cooler semi-humid conditions and more significant diurnal temperature variation, this region fosters slower grape maturation, better acid retention, and nuanced aromatic profiles. While not yet developed commercially (with no registered producers according to official records), the region is drawing attention for its potential to yield premium white wines and lighter reds that differ stylistically from southern production. Its development is central to diversification and climate resilience within the national wine strategy.

The Nudo Viticultural Region, defined by higher elevations (400–500 meters) and rugged karst terrain, exemplifies the adaptation of Montenegrin viticulture to climate pressures. Though relatively small in scale, it offers distinct microclimates and soil conditions suitable for the cultivation of grape varieties that thrive in moderate climates. Wines from Nudo are marked by vibrant acidity, aromatic freshness, and balanced phenolic structure. While still underutilised, this region is emblematic of the potential to relocate vineyards toward more climate-resilient zones, a strategy that may become essential in the coming decades.

Montenegrin vineyards are dominated by autochthonous grape varieties, which not only preserve cultural identity but also offer a competitive edge on the global market. Red grape varieties account for 69% of total cultivation, white grapes 23%, and table grapes 8%. Local varieties make up more than 86% of total grape production, with key representatives including Vranac, Kratošija, Krstač, and Žižak, all of which display distinctive organoleptic profiles shaped by Montenegro's diverse terroirs. Vranac, in particular, is the dominant variety, cultivated on over 80% of vineyard areas, and is widely recognised as a symbol of Montenegrin viticulture. This grape yields deeply colored, full-bodied red wines and has been the subject of extensive clonal selection, culminating in the official recognition of seven clones in 2014, aimed at enhancing yield, sugar-acid balance, and overall quality while safeguarding genetic integrity.

Wines made from autochthonous grape varieties represent the majority of overall wine production in Montenegro and are well represented in both the domestic and international markets. In parallel, Montenegro also cultivates international grape varieties such as Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot, and Chardonnay, which are successfully integrated into the national wine portfolio and contribute to exports. Alongside monovarietal wines, both indigenous and international varieties are commonly blended, resulting in unique and expressive wines that combine tradition with innovation. These blends have proven to be commercially and qualitatively successful, enriching the diversity of Montenegro's wine offering and enhancing its competitiveness on global markets. Surface structure of red wine varieties in Montenegro is given in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Surface Structure of Red Wine Varieties in Montenegro.

Montenegro's viticultural richness extends beyond its main commercial varieties. A comprehensive genotyping study in collaboration with the La Rioja Institute revealed 144 unique grape genotypes from 476 cultivated and wild vines, of which 51 were previously undocumented. This includes 43 wild vines and 101 cultivated genotypes, showcasing Montenegro as a genetic reservoir of grapevine biodiversity. Among notable discoveries is the parentage of Vranac, confirmed to be a cross between Kratošija (father) and Duljenga (mother). In 2016, the company 13. Jul – Plantaže established a National Collection of local and neglected varieties at Ćemovsko Polje, preserving genetic diversity and supporting future resilience against climate change, drought, and pests.

In terms of production, 13. Jul – Plantaže remains the cornerstone of the national wine industry, managing over 2,100ha of vineyards and producing nearly 9 million litres of wine annually. Vineyards in this estate and others are typically planted at low altitudes (<100m), with intensive mechanisation and precision viticulture tools increasingly employed. Despite the dominance of large producers, small and medium-sized wineries across the coastal and emerging highland regions are gaining recognition for boutique wines and enotourism experiences.

Training systems vary depending on use: commercial vineyards rely primarily on single-cane Guyot and horizontal cordon systems, typically with trunk heights between 60–80cm, while pergola systems (beds) are common in residential zones for table grapes. Some traditional vineyards still maintain Gobelet-trained vines, preserving Montenegro's historical heritage. Modernisation is visible, but care is taken to retain cultural viticultural practices where possible.

Montenegro's wine sector stands at a crossroads between tradition and innovation. Its viticultural landscape is defined by centuries-old grape varieties, diverse climate zones, and adaptive strategies, making it a unique and promising player in the broader European wine ecosystem.

2.2. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Agriculture plays an important role in the economic and social development of Montenegro. In 2023, the sector contributed over 7.6% to the national GDP, demonstrating its substantial economic significance. Family farms remain the backbone of Montenegrin agriculture, employing nearly a quarter of the country's total workforce. This highlights its crucial role in sustainable development, mitigating rural depopulation, and preserving traditional livelihoods. Beyond its direct economic contribution, agriculture is deeply intertwined with other priority sectors, particularly tourism. These synergies are evident in the integration of traditional gastronomy within Montenegro's broader tourism offerings, reinforcing the country's cultural identity and boosting economic opportunities for rural communities.

Viticulture and winemaking represent an important segment of Montenegrin agriculture, contributing not only to economic growth but also to cultural and tourism development. Wine production has long been a staple of Montenegro's agricultural exports, with total wine exports reaching 13.4 million euros in 2023. Despite an overall increase in the import of agri-food products and a growing trade deficit in 2024, wine remains one of the country's most valuable export commodities. The largest markets for Montenegrin wine exports include Serbia (7.4 million euros) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (2.5 million euros). Further, supporting local wine production through investment in precision viticulture, technological advancements, and enhanced market accessibility could further strengthen its role in the national economy.

A significant development impacting the wine sector is the introduction of a new excise tax policy on wine. As of 2024, Montenegro has implemented an excise tax of 25 euros per hectoliter on still wines, which previously had no excise duty. Small wine producers, defined as those producing up to 1,000 hectoliters annually, benefit from a reduced rate of 12.5 euros per hectoliter. While this measure aligns Montenegro's fiscal policies with EU standards and aims to generate additional state revenue, it also presents challenges for local wine producers. One of the most affected companies is 13 - Jul Plantaže, Montenegro's largest wine producer, which estimates an annual cost increase of approximately one million euros due to the new tax. This is expected to lead to a 14% to 20% increase in retail wine prices, potentially impacting consumer demand and competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

Looking ahead, the future of viticulture in Montenegro depends on its ability to adapt to evolving market demands, climate change challenges, and global sustainability trends. Policies aimed at increasing domestic production capacities, reducing import dependency, and enhancing the competitiveness of Montenegrin wines on international markets are necessary to ensure long-term resilience. This includes strategies for relocating vineyards to higher altitudes or more climate-resilient regions, as well as adopting more heat- and drought-tolerant grape varieties or changing rootstocks to improve resilience against shifting climate conditions. Investments in digitalisation, including the implementation of geospatial monitoring tools, precision agriculture technologies, and decision-support systems, will further enhance efficiency, sustainability, and climate resilience within the sector. Research and innovation will play a critical role in this transformation, driving the development of new cultivation techniques, climate adaptation strategies, and improved grapevine genetics. Strengthening collaboration with research institutions, both nationally and internationally, will be essential for fostering innovation in wine production.

Additionally, integrating viticulture with tourism presents significant opportunities for rural development and economic diversification, enhancing the visibility of Montenegrin wines, creating new income streams, and strengthening the country's cultural identity as a premium wine destination. Finally, fostering regional cooperation and participation in European research and funding programs will provide Montenegrin wine producers with opportunities for knowledge exchange, improved production techniques, and better market positioning, ensuring the sector remains competitive in the face of global challenges.

Mitigation strategies should also be integrated to reduce the environmental impact of viticulture. Efficient machinery, reduced chemical inputs, and the adoption of organic farming practices can help lower greenhouse gas emissions from vineyards. Adjusting harvesting schedules to minimise heat exposure and optimising transport logistics to reduce fuel consumption are additional steps toward sustainability. The combination of adaptation and mitigation strategies will ensure that Montenegrin viticulture remains competitive while addressing both short-term and long-term challenges posed by climate change.

As viticulture continues to evolve, the sector's socio-economic impact will remain significant. By promoting policies that support small and medium-sized wine producers, encouraging sustainable practices, and leveraging the country's unique terroirs, Montenegro has the potential to further establish itself as a key player in the regional and international wine industry. The future perspectives of Montenegrin viticulture hinge on the balance between preserving traditional winemaking practices and embracing modern innovations that enhance productivity and sustainability. With a strategic approach to economic planning and investment, the viticulture sector will continue to play a vital role in the socio-economic landscape of Montenegro.

3

Effects of climate change on Montenegrin viticulture

Effects of climate change on Montenegrin viticulture

SUMMARY

Climate change is expected to significantly threaten the viticulture sector in the 21st century (**Santos et al., 2020; van Leeuwen et al., 2024**). The influence of ambient climate on winemaking has been studied for centuries, highlighting the high sensitivity of *Vitis vinifera* to climatic conditions. However, the anticipated changes in climate are unprecedented, and traditional adaptation measures may no longer be sufficient to ensure sustainability (**Tscholl et al., 2024**). Given this sensitivity, detailed and robust projections of future climate change are necessary. Furthermore, climate conditions will not change uniformly across the globe. For instance, while many regions are expected to experience increased precipitation, the Mediterranean – including Montenegro – is projected to undergo significant warming and drying trends (**Fernandes et al., 2024**). For Montenegrin winegrowers, developing and implementing effective adaptation strategies will be essential to maintaining high-quality wine production and remaining competitive in both regional and international markets. However, this requires highly localised climate projections, given Montenegro's diverse topography and microclimates.

3.1. CLIMATE CHANGE IN MONTENEGRO

Montenegro exhibits diverse climatic conditions, ranging from warm and humid coastal areas to a more continental climate in the central region and colder mountainous conditions in the east (**Fernandes et al., 2024**). During the vine-growing season (March to September), the climate is generally characterised by hot and relatively dry conditions, with coastal areas experiencing more rainfall compared to the drier and cooler mountainous regions.

Over the past two decades, global climate change has led to a significant temperature increase of up to 1.3°C during the vegetation period.

Future climate projections indicate an even more pronounced warming trend. In addition to rising temperatures, climate change is expected to introduce further challenges that could adversely affect Montenegro's agricultural sector, with vineyards being particularly vulnerable.

According to the CHELSA-ISIMIP3b (Karger et al., 2017) future climate projections, temperatures during the vine-growing season are expected to rise by 2.1 to 6.4°C by the end of the 21st century (2071–2100) compared to the baseline period of 1981–2010. The extent of warming will depend on future greenhouse gas concentrations, ranging from the low-emission SSP1-2.6 scenario to the high-emission SSP5-8.5 scenario. Figure 3 illustrates the spatial distribution of projected temperature and precipitation changes.

While temperatures are expected to increase, precipitation is projected to decline across Montenegro by up to 0.8mm/day (a total reduction of ~200mm from March to September). This will intensify the ongoing drying trend due to increased evapotranspiration and reduced rainfall.

Figure 3: Temperature (left) and precipitation (right) changes for the two scenarios SSP1-2.6 (top) and SSP5-8.5 (bottom) for the period 2071–2100 compared to 1981–2010. The changes are calculated as ensemble mean changes of the CHELSA-ISIMIP3b ensemble (9 models). Areas with statistical insignificant changes (10% significance level) are shaded.

Table 1: Evaluation of various climate indices for 4 different regions of Montenegro. For each index and regions the central black number refers to the observed absolute values for the period 1981–2010. The upper red number refers to the changes for the SSP5–8.5 scenario, while the lower green number refers to the changes for the SSP1–2.6 scenario. The anticipated future changes are calculated for the period 2071–2100 compared to 1981–2010. All changes are ensemble median changes for the CHLSA–ISIMIP3b ensemble (9 models).

Index	Montenegro	Coastal Region	Central Region	Northern Region
DJF temperature [°C]	-0.5 +4.6 +1.9	4.1 +4.4 +1.8	0.7 +4.5 +1.8	-2.5 +4.7 +1.9
JJA temperature [°C]	17.7 +7.8 +2.5	21.5 +7.5 +2.6	18.7 +7.7 +2.6	16.1 +7.9 +2.5
DJF precipitation [mm/d]	5.4 -0.2 +0.2	6.2 -0.3 +0.3	6.2 -0.2 +0.3	4.6 -0.1 +0.3
JJA precipitation [mm/d]	2.2 -0.7 +0.2	1.8 -0.6 +0.2	2.1 -0.7 +0.2	2.3 -0.7 +0.2
MAMJJAS number of hot days [d]	9.3 +60.3 +16.0	26.5 +76.4 +29.3	11.9 +65.5 +18.8	3.5 +52.8 +10.8
MAMJJAS number of summer days [d]	40.0 +69.6 +27.5	80.6 +60.1 +27.8	47.6 +70.4 +29.5	25.2 +72.7 +26.0
MAMJJAS number of tropical nights [d]	3.6 +42.8 +6.3	14.0 +66.6 +19.5	5.1 +47.8 +8.6	0.2 +32.6 +1.6
MAM number of frost days [d]	26.6 -15.6 -7.0	10.4 -7.9 -3.9	21.5 -13.7 -6.4	34.0 -18.7 -8.3
MAM number of ice days [d]	3.5 -2.8 -1.8	0.4 -0.3 -0.2	2.1 -1.8 -1.1	5.3 -4.2 -2.6
DJF number of frost damage days [d]	13.1 -11.6 -7.0	2.2 -2.1 -1.5	8.3 -7.7 -5.2	18.8 -16.5 -9.3
MAM maximum consecutive number of dry days [d]	12.0 +1.9 +0.2	13.5 +2.7 +0.6	12.3 +2.0 +0.3	11.5 +1.7 +0.1
JJA maximum consecutive number of dry days [d]	17.8 +4.8 +2.0	21.7 +6.6 +3.5	18.9 +5.1 +2.2	16.2 +4.2 +1.6
MAM potential evapotranspiration [mm/d]	2.4 +0.5 +0.2	2.8 +0.6 +0.2	2.5 +0.6 +0.2	2.2 +0.6 +0.2
JJA potential evapotranspiration [mm/d]	4.3 +1.2 +0.5	4.8 +1.3 +0.5	4.4 +1.2 +0.5	4.1 +1.2 +0.4
growing season length [d]	236.3 +67.3 +25.6	306.1 +46.3 +24.0	252.0 +69.4 +28.2	209.2 +72.0 +24.7

These climatic shifts will have profound effects on agriculture and particularly viticulture production. Table 1 presents changes in key climate indices relevant to vineyard management. The most pronounced warming and drying is projected for the already arid summer months (June to August), significantly impacting grape development and maturation. Even under the lowest-emission scenario (SSP1-2.6), the number of hot days and tropical nights is expected to at least double. As a result, vines will experience more frequent heat stress and reduced nighttime cooling, conditions that affect grape quality and yield.

Higher temperatures will also accelerate phenological development, leading to an earlier bud break and an extended growing season, ranging from 24 to 72 additional days. While this might be seen as a climate change benefit, it also poses a considerable threat. As vine development will start early during a period still prone to frost damage. Although the frequency of frost and ice events is projected to decline in winter and spring, they will not disappear entirely, even under the high-emission SSP5-8.5 scenario. This is particularly relevant for the mountainous northern regions of Montenegro, where frost events below 10°C could still occur up to twice per year, posing a risk to vines even during dormancy. Furthermore, an earlier development will also lead to a shift of the grape maturity phase towards the hotter summer months, resulting in a shorter maturity phase and grapes with higher sugar and lower acid content, ultimately resulting in lower quality wines.

In addition to reduced precipitation, the duration of dry spells is expected to increase by up to one week, particularly in summer over Montenegro's coastal and central regions. This will further exacerbate water stress, increasing the demand for irrigation to offset evapotranspiration, which is projected to rise between 9% and 29%.

Bioclimatic indices are often used to portray climate conditions for grape growing, such as Growing Season Average Temperature (GST) (Figure 4) or Winkler Index (Figure 5). Similarly, the growing season average temperature contributes to assessing climatic compatibility for viticulture by evaluating the optimal temperature during the growing season. The Winkler Index classifies regions based on the accumulation of active temperatures ($>10^{\circ}\text{C}$) during the growing season.

These types of indices are relevant to select the possible grape varieties to cultivate, for example, according to Jones et al., 2010, Regions Ia and Ib (Figure 5) are suitable for early ripening varieties, while Region V is suitable for the production of table wines. For specific grape varieties, Jones 2018 suggests growing season temperature ranges, for example, 13°C to 15°C for Müller-Thurgau, while 16°C to 22°C for Table grape varieties. As seen in the case of Montenegro in the historical period, the territory covers a wide variety of climate conditions for wine growing (Figure 4) and (Figure 5), ranging from an average GST of 6°C to 21°C , and a Winkler index covering all classes I, II, III, IV and V. Under future scenarios, with the temperature increase, is seen across the basin of Lake Skadar, values of the Winkler Index are above the Region V threshold, and GST is higher than 22°C . These conditions are uncommon among traditional wine-growing regions and present significant challenges for viticulture. With the implementation of targeted adaptation strategies supported by scientific and technological advancements, it remains possible to sustain grape cultivation and wine production even in the most climate-affected areas.

Figure 4: Nine-member ensemble mean of global circulation model experiments for the growing season average temperature, for the periods 1995–2014 and 2041–2060. A) for the historical period, B) for the future period under the SSP1-2.6, C) for the future period under the SSP3-7.0 and D) for the future period under the SSP5-8.5.

Figure 5: Nine-member ensemble mean of global circulation model experiments for the Winkler Index, for the periods 1995–2014 and 2041–2060. A) for the historical period, B) for the future period under the SSP1-2.6, C) for the future period under the SSP3-7.0 and D) for the future period under the SSP5-8.5.

3.2. CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON MONTENEGRIN VITICULTURE

The impacts of climate change on Montenegrin viticulture are certain, and adaptation measures are needed to counter them. But, to what degree will it affect different aspects of viticulture? The temperature increase and precipitation are expected; consequently, without implementing and improving suitable adaptation measures, there will be a decrease in grape yield and changes in wine quality.

Some changes are affecting the sector according to the conducted questionnaire, addressed to professionals in the viticulture sector. According to the sector (Figure 7), the most noted effect is the increase in hailstorms, which physically damage vineyards. Hailstorms are frequent in Montenegro, but hard to predict. Hereinafter, sunburn damage, thermal stress, aridity and drought are noted effects, which are a direct consequence of the temperature increase. When it comes to changes in grapevine development, the sector clearly depicts the occurrence of earlier key phenological phases (Fraga et al., 2024), more notably on budbreak and maturation (Figure 8).

Globally, climate change impacts on viticulture are different from region to region. However, the changes reported by the sector (Figure 7, Figure 8) can be confirmed by scientific evidence when it comes to earlier phenological events occurrence (Figure 6) and yield decrease. Other changes, like an increase in pests and diseases and a reduction in water availability, are indicated by the grapevine growers.

Changes in the phenological cycle are among the best documented impacts of climate change on viticulture (Jones et al., 2005; van Leeuwen et al., 2019). Since temperature is the primary driver of phenological development, projected temperature increases can be reliably translated into shifts in vine phenology. Multiple modelling approaches have been applied, and despite methodological differences, they consistently project similar shifts, which strengthens the robustness of these findings. Phenological responses, however, are not only influenced by the overall rise in mean annual temperature but are also particularly sensitive to the seasonal distribution of warming. As a result, different developmental phases of the vine may shift to varying extents.

For grape vine in general, the most critical phenological stages include bud and leaf development, inflorescence, flowering, fruit development, and ripening. Each of these stages can be further broken down into specific developmental steps, which can be quantitatively assessed using the BBCH scale (Lorenz et al., 1995). To evaluate the impacts of climate change on vine phenology in Montenegro, we analyse shifts in the multi-year average day of the year (DOY) on which specific BBCH steps occur for 3 different future socio-economic scenarios (see Riahi et al., 2017 for details): SSP1-2.7 (sustainability), SSP3-7.0 (regional rivalry) and SSP5-8.5 (fossil-fueled development). Furthermore, we can analyse the length of each stage as it represents how rapidly the development of the grape vine progresses.

Similar to many wine-growing regions worldwide, climate change impacts on Montenegrin viticulture are characterised by a pronounced advancement of phenological stages, distinct changes in the duration of phenological phases, and an expansion of viticulturally suitable areas. Figure 6 illustrates the DOY for bud break (BBCH 09), full flowering (BBCH 65), end of fruit development (BBCH 79), and end of ripening (BBCH 89) for the historical period (1981-2010) and for the three future scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5) for 2071-2100, for the variety Vranac. During the historical period, areas suitable for viticulture, defined as those where Vranac reaches the end of ripening, were mainly confined to coastal regions and lowland areas, particularly the Zeta Plain near Podgorica. The mountainous northeastern part of Montenegro has traditionally been unsuitable for viticulture, with the exception of localised sites such as Bijelo Polje (see Section 2.1). Under all future scenarios, however, suitable areas expand substantially, even under the low-emission pathway SSP1-2.6. Under SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5, climatic conditions are projected to become suitable for Vranac cultivation across nearly all of Montenegro. It is important to note that this assessment is based solely on temperature suitability and does not account for other terroir-defining factors such as soil characteristics and water availability.

Beyond the expansion of climatically suitable areas, the projected advancement of phenological development is particularly noteworthy. Under SSP5-8.5, phenological phases are projected to advance by more than one month relative to the historical baseline. Such changes will necessitate adjustments in vineyard management timing and may alter grape composition, particularly the sugar-to-acid ratio, thereby influencing overall wine quality. Consequently, some regions may become less suitable for the production of high-quality wine despite improved thermal conditions. Additionally, the earlier onset of bud break, potentially occurring as early as late February, could expose vines to a higher risk of late frost damage, even under future warming conditions. Under the low-emission scenario SSP1-2.6, phenological advancements remain moderate, ranging between 10 and 20 days. Still, the advancement is already perceived by the majority of the sector (Figure 7).

In the Zeta Plain and coastal regions, the advancement of phenological stages differs from that observed in inland and higher-elevation areas. While stages up to the end of fruit development are projected to advance by 10 to 40 days depending on the emission pathway, the end of the ripening phase (maturation) shows little or no advancement. In contrast, the sector perceives earlier maturation (Figure 7) because currently, increasing temperatures are advancing the development. However, the projected maturation results (with no changes) resemble stagnation from excessive heat stress that impedes normal ripening progression (Greer and Weston, 2010).

Figure 6: Projected changes in the day of year (DOY) of key phenological stages: bud break (BBCH 09), full flowering (BBCH 65), end of fruit development (BBCH 79), and end of ripening (BBCH 89), for the grapevine variety Vranac in Montenegro. Results are shown for the historical period (1981-2010) and three future climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, SSP5-8.5) for 2071-2100.

Simulations for the *Vitis vinifera* variety Vranac, performed using the UNIFI.GrapeML model (Leolini et al., 2018, 2023), indicated a general advancement of the maturity date under future climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5) compared to the current scenario, with an average advancement of approximately 22 days across all five simulation sites considered in this study. This phenological shift, combined with thermal and water stress, leads to a reduction in fruit biomass, already perceived by the sector, by a decrease in grape yield (Figure 6).

Future projections indicate an average decrease of at least ~1.6t/ha (equivalent to 32.1g of dry matter m⁻², assuming a grape moisture content of ~80%). This corresponds to an average yield loss of about 21%, underscoring the need for targeted agronomic strategies to optimise vine productivity under changing climate conditions.

Although intrinsic limitations related to crop model approach calibration and application (e.g. comprehensive observed data for calibration, potential variations in future agronomic practices, etc.) may increase the uncertainty of the simulations, further investigations to validate these results are needed. The findings presented in this report provide new insights into the trends and variability of grape yields, which inevitably affect the sustainability of viticulture in Montenegro under current and future scenarios.

WITNESSED ANY CHANGE?

Figure 7: Witnessed changes in viticulture and winemaking sector.

WITNESSED ANY CHANGE?

Figure 8: Witnessed changes in grapevine phenology.

4

Precision farming

Precision farming

SUMMARY

Advances in precision farming are reshaping viticulture by enabling a more detailed understanding of vineyard dynamics and their interaction with environmental conditions. Through the integration of remote sensing, proximal sensing, and digital platforms, vineyard management can shift from uniform practices to spatially and temporally targeted interventions. These technologies allow winegrowers to monitor vine health, soil conditions, and microclimatic variability with unprecedented accuracy, supporting more efficient use of water, inputs, and labour. Within this context, digital decision-support tools act as a bridge between complex datasets and practical vineyard management, facilitating timely responses to climate-related risks.

4.1. REMOTE SENSING

Remote sensing is a tool for viticulture that allows precise monitoring of what is happening in the crop and the surrounding environment. Remote sensing is defined as the process of gathering information without physical contact. Information is collected from a distance using sensors, which are mounted on satellites or drones (Figure 9). These devices collect spectral data from the soil and grapevines, and indices (such as NDVI) are estimated, which are then translated into information on the local crop (e.g., soil moisture, pests and diseases, yield and quality estimation).

It is preferable to use drones to collect data in the field, allowing a spatial resolution that can be as high as 1cm, and the sampling periods can be controlled by vineyard managers. In smaller areas, the use of drones can be more cost-effective than satellites; however, there are costs for the acquisition of the equipment, maintenance and energy for charging. Data from satellites is freely available and can cover most areas. But the disadvantages (compared to drones) are that the maximum spatial resolution is around 10 meters, and the time resolution is about 1 week for data derived from image processing.

Figure 9: Use of drones for remote sensing and precision monitoring in vineyards.

At first sight, remote sensing is hard to understand and requires expertise to analyse the data and translate it into indicators for the vineyards (e.g, yield, moisture, vigour). However, with the current advances in automation and the IoT, the information can be easily accessed by grape growers through friendly user platforms, giving also alerts on specific crop needs, such as when and where and when should be irrigated, fertilise, or even when pests and diseases are affecting the crop. For large companies, using part of the R&D resources to do this monitoring can be profitable. Still, for smaller grape growers, platforms can be accessed through consulting companies that provide these services, or to partner with research projects from universities, or research centres, as in the MONTEVITIS project.

4.2. PROXIMAL SENSING

Proximal sensing is a key technology in modern precision viticulture, providing real-time, high-resolution data for monitoring vineyard conditions at a local scale. Unlike remote sensing, which relies on satellite or Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) imagery, proximal sensing utilises ground-based sensors placed within the vineyard to continuously measure critical variables such as soil moisture, nutrient levels, canopy vigour, and microclimatic conditions. This allows for detailed spatial and temporal monitoring, enabling winegrowers to assess vineyard condition and make informed management decisions tailored to specific zones within their fields. The ability to collect precise, location-specific data enhances efficient resource utilisation by optimising irrigation, fertilisation, and pest control measures.

By integrating proximal sensing technologies, viticulturists can improve crop health and yield predictability while mitigating the risks posed by weather variability. The continuous monitoring of soil and plant conditions helps identify early signs of stress, such as drought or nutrient deficiencies, allowing for timely interventions (Figure 10). Georeferenced yield and quality data facilitate better vineyard zoning, ensuring that grapes of different ripening profiles are managed accordingly to achieve optimal quality. The integration of these datasets with advanced analytics and decision-support tools strengthens long-term sustainability by enhancing soil conservation and supporting timely adaptation strategies to changing environmental conditions.

The benefits of proximal sensing extend beyond operational efficiency, but also contribute to the broader goals of environmental sustainability in viticulture. By enabling targeted interventions, these technologies minimise the overuse of water, fertilisers, and pesticides, reducing the ecological footprint of vineyards. The data collected from proximal sensors plays a crucial role in refining measures for adapting to climate change, allowing growers to adjust row orientation and vineyard practices based on real-time environmental feedback. As viticulture faces increasing challenges due to climate change, the adoption of proximal sensing offers a science-driven approach to ensure resilience, sustainability, and improved wine quality.

Figure 10: Proximal sensor monitoring vineyard conditions.

4.3. DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM

A DSS for viticulture is a digital platform designed to assist grape growers, agronomists, and policymakers in making informed decisions based on data and predictive insights. It integrates various sources of information—such as real-time weather and sensor data, phenological observations, and climate projections—into a unified system that supports vineyard monitoring and management. Through intuitive dashboards, geospatial visualisation, and alert mechanisms, the DSS enables users to track vine development, assess risks (e.g. disease or drought), and optimise interventions like irrigation and pesticide use. By translating complex data into practical, actionable guidance, the DSS promotes more efficient, sustainable, and climate-resilient viticultural practices.

In many European regions, DSSs such as VitiMeteo (Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Luxembourg), XFARM (Italy, Spain, France, Poland), Hort@ (Italy), AgroClimWeb (France), and VineSens (Spain) are widely used by local grape growers. These systems provide a range of services including disease and pest risk forecasting, phenology modelling, irrigation scheduling, and climate analysis—helping producers to make informed, timely, and environmentally responsible decisions in vineyard management. Since in Montenegro, such a DSS for viticulture does not exist, in the framework of the MONTEVITIS project, a DSS tailored for the Montenegrin viticultural industry is developed, focusing on the specific needs of the local producers that are identified via workshops and questionnaires organised with the grape growers (Figure 11-13).

Figure 11: Preview of MONTEVITIS DSS.

Figure 12: MONTEVITIS DSS map of minimum temperature distribution.

Figure 13: MONTEVITIS DSS view of vineyard sensor data.

The MONTEVITIS DSS is implemented as a comprehensive web-based platform designed to support vineyard stakeholders through integrated access to data, models, and visual tools. At its foundation, the platform includes a structured registry of all wine producers in Montenegro, providing detailed information on their vineyard parcels, planted grape varieties, and historical yields (Simeunović et al., 2025). This centralised dataset allows producers and policymakers to understand spatial patterns of viticultural activity, assess productivity at the variety and parcel level, and benchmark performance across regions. By enabling continuous updates and tracking of vineyard assets, the platform supports efficient vineyard management and facilitates evidence-based decision-making.

Another key functionality of the DSS is the real-time visualisation of IoT sensor data from vineyards equipped with field devices. These sensors measure critical agro-environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, precipitation, and soil moisture. By accessing live and historical measurements through intuitive dashboards, producers can respond promptly to field conditions, optimising irrigation, adjusting protection strategies, and mitigating climate-induced risks. The ability to detect stress factors early contributes directly to improved grape quality and yield stability, while also promoting more sustainable resource use.

In addition to real-time monitoring, the DSS offers structured tools for managing phenological observations and field activities. Producers can record dates of key growth stages (e.g. budburst, flowering, ripening) and log vineyard interventions such as pruning, spraying, and irrigation. This functionality enables producers to maintain detailed records of vineyard performance and management practices, which in turn supports traceability, compliance with agricultural standards, and improved planning. Researchers benefit from access to harmonised phenological datasets for model calibration and climate impact studies.

One of the platform's most strategic components is its climate projection and bioclimatic index module. Leveraging downscaled regional climate models, the system provides spatial and temporal visualisations of both historical and future climate conditions across Montenegro. Users can explore trends in temperature and precipitation under multiple climate scenarios, alongside computed indices such as the Huglin Index and Cool Night Index. These insights are crucial for assessing the long-term suitability of grape varieties, identifying zones vulnerable to heat or drought, and planning adaptation strategies such as varietal replacement or vineyard relocation.

Finally, the DSS is being expanded with simulation and modelling capabilities that will enable scenario analysis and risk forecasting. Planned features include predictive modelling of yields based on climate and field data, simulation of disease pressure under variable weather conditions, and forecasting of water stress to inform irrigation decisions. These tools will allow users not only to understand current conditions but to anticipate future outcomes, improving strategic planning and reducing uncertainty in an increasingly volatile climate. Through its integrated, multi-layered functionality, the DSS empowers vineyard managers, researchers, and policymakers to make informed, timely, and forward-looking decisions in support of resilient and sustainable viticulture.

5

Adaptation and mitigation measures

Adaptation and mitigation measures

SUMMARY

As climate change intensifies, the ability of vineyards to adapt while reducing their environmental footprint becomes a central challenge for the sustainability of viticulture. A wide range of adaptation measures, spanning irrigation management, canopy and training system adjustments, soil practices, and pest control strategies, are already being applied or tested in Montenegrin vineyards. These practices aim to buffer climate extremes, preserve grape quality, and stabilise yields under increasing stress. At the same time, mitigation measures contribute to lowering greenhouse gas emissions and reducing reliance on chemical inputs, aligning viticulture with broader environmental objectives. When supported by monitoring technologies and data-driven decision-making, adaptation and mitigation form a complementary framework for enhancing resilience and ensuring the long-term viability of the wine sector.

5.1. ADAPTATION MEASURES

Adaptation measures to climate change impacts in viticulture are important to safeguard the economic sustainability of the sector. How these measures are presently implemented by the Montenegrin winegrowers will be discussed in the following chapter. Results are based on interviews with winegrowers, a questionnaire and experiences of the members of the MONTEVITIS (Figure 14).

IS IT APPLIED IN THE VINEYARDS?

Figure 14: Result of the questionnaire after the workshop.

Changes in canopy management and harvest date

Changes in canopy management can aim (i) to delay maturity and (ii) to reduce water consumption. Examples are changes in canopy geometry and leaf removal above the cluster zone to reduce the assimilation surface (Santos et al. 2020). Up to now, Montenegrin winegrowers haven't changed the canopy geometry while leaf removal is applied. Early leaf removal is preferred to let the berries adapt to the sun, already at an early development stage. Other crop cultural adaptation measures, like delayed shoot trimming or trimming at higher shoot length to have more shade, have changed as well.

Other strategies applied are an earlier harvest, as it is already done at 13. Jul Plantaže to produce sparkling wine. As an example, Chardonnay is harvested earlier to preserve an accurate level of acidity instead of targeting an optimal aroma maturity.

Application of sunscreens

Sunburn is negatively affecting yield and wine quality and is likely to occur more often, as the frequency of extreme heatwaves will increase. Several inert compounds, such as kaolin or calcium carbonate, that serve as sunscreen (Santos et al. 2020), can be sprayed to prevent damage from sunburn on grapes. These natural compounds are listed as plant-strengthening agents. Winegrowers in Montenegro are not widely using these compounds so far; it is one adaptation measure which is less applied in Montenegrin vineyards, but two years of research were carried out at 13. Jul – Plantaže on the application of calcium carbonate as a sun-protecting measure (Bakić et al. 2025). Additionally, Kaolin will be tested in future.

Figure 15: Kaolin on grapes of defoliated vines

Shading

Other methods to protect the grapevines from heat and irradiance are shading nets, planting trees in the vineyards or installing a Viti-photovoltaic system. Shading is widely applied (79%) in Montenegrin vineyards according to the questionnaire, but it is less applied than other measures, such as soil management or adapting the training system (Figure 14). Montenegrin winegrowers are using nets only in a few vineyards, usually for multiple purposes, for shading and protection against hail and insects.

The most perceived changes due to climate change are the following: frequency of hailstorms, thermal stress, drought and sunburn damage (Figure 15). Shading nets can also efficiently protect berries from sunburn and provide other advantages to meet the challenges of climate change, such as a prolonged ripening period, leading to higher acidity and lower sugar and alcohol contents in wine. However, phenolic concentration is usually decreased due to shading, and it can affect yield negatively (Pallotti et al. 2023). Hail nets can also be used for shading to benefit from both the positive shading effects and the protection from hailstorms (Pallotti et al. 2025). Trees are usually not planted for shading in Montenegrin vineyards, but they might serve as a windbreak belt. Viti-photovoltaic is discussed and might become important in future. Both could become an important adaptation measure to climate change in the future for Montenegro.

Trees are usually not planted for shading in Montenegrin vineyards, but they might serve as a windbreak belt. Viti-photovoltaic is discussed and might become important in future. Both could become an important adaptation measure to climate change in the future for Montenegro.

Irrigation and Infrastructure for water storage

The implementation of irrigation systems has increased across European vineyards, even though they are traditionally rainfed. Grapevines need to be irrigated when precipitation is too low and yield and quality need to be improved (Santos et al. 2020). In Montenegro, nearly all (around 98%) of the vineyards are irrigated, which is also reflected in the responses to the questionnaire (Figure 14). In 2024, the irrigation season started significantly later compared to previous years, due to higher precipitation in spring. Usually, irrigation starts at the beginning of June, with one irrigation cycle for 24h, then it is repeated every 5 to 7 days. However, in August 2024, the irrigation frequency had to be increased due to warm and dry June and July conditions, which could become more frequent in future years.

Under future climate conditions, the irrigation demand might increase across Europe; simultaneously, water availability will become a limiting factor, especially in the Mediterranean area (Santos et al. 2020). This emphasises the need for infrastructure for water storage. In Montenegro, winegrowers most often have wells, or they use swimming pools or cisterns to store water for irrigation.

Pest and disease control

A changing climate might present favourable conditions for invasive pests and diseases, for example, a shift in the distribution area of leafhoppers, which can function as vectors of different diseases. The risk of pests and diseases might increase in some wine-growing regions, whereas the demand for reducing pesticide applications is high. Higher growing season temperatures above 22°C might lead to drought stress in dry climates, while in humid climates, it can cause higher disease pressures. (Santos et al. 2020). Furthermore, winegrowers need to adapt to more frequent extreme weather conditions. For example, rainy periods in summer can cause severe fungal disease pressure (Molitor et al. 2025).

Fundamental for pest and disease control is crop monitoring, which has been done until now visually in Montenegrin vineyards. Insect traps with pheromones for monitoring grape berry moth population development are used in the Plantaže estate. Additionally, digital traps have been used experimentally here.

MONTEVITIS DSS provides integrated tools for pest and disease monitoring and forecasting, supporting targeted and reduced use of pesticides.

Soil management

Effective soil management is crucial for soil protection, particularly in conserving water and carbon. As a result, tillage is discouraged (Santos et al. 2020). At 13. Jul – Plantaže, this approach is implemented by maintaining natural vegetation cover, which is periodically mowed or shredded. Private winemakers in Montenegro are increasingly adopting the practice of covering the entire vineyard with natural vegetation. Only the area between the vines is cultivated. Cover crops are usually not used; however, some winegrowers have recently started using grass mixtures (Figure 16). The application of mulching is not common. However, one winegrower is testing mulching films in a young vineyard. In addition, ongoing research on compost applications is being conducted in some vineyards, both during the growing season and vineyard establishment, in combination with manure.

Figure 16: Cover crops growing between vine rows

Adapting the training system

Changes in the training system aim at delaying the maturation period, lowering the sugar accumulation due to lower canopy heights or a reduction of sunlight in the cluster zone. Changes in the training system can also include a change of row orientation, trunk height or planting density to lower radiation, temperature and sugar accumulation (Santos et al. 2020). The most used training systems in Montenegro are the single-cane Guyot, single- and double-arm horizontal cordon. As part of the experimental work in 13. Jul – Plantaže, new training systems for table grape varieties are being implemented. Horizontal trellising systems, such as the pergola tendone and raised training forms, are introduced. Besides the experimental pergola tendone and high trunk (1.8m), the standard height in trellises in Plantaže is 60-80 cm, and this is not supposed to change. The situation is similar in the private sector, with the occasional presence of pergolas in private plots, where the height can exceed 2 meters. In most vineyards in Montenegro, the row orientation is north-south.

Recently, some winegrowers have been adjusting the orientation to a slight angle to allow the morning sun to dominate over the afternoon sunlight. This should prevent an overheating of grapes during the hottest days of the year and preserve the acidity in grapes (Minaar et al. 2022, Hunter et al. 2017). Changes in planting density can be another measure to adapt to climate change, in 13. Jul – Plantaže, no change in planting density is envisaged (4800 to 5500 plants per ha), spacing of 0.7-0.8m x 2.6m. Some private winegrowers increased the plant spacing to 0.9m or 1.0m, depending on the variety and environmental conditions.

Changing rootstock

Changing rootstocks towards more drought-resistant ones might be the most important measure concerning plant water availability (Santos et al. 2020). In Montenegro, the main rootstock is 1103 Paulsen, which is considered drought-resistant. On sandy and gravelly soils – permeable soils, which are predominantly found in the Plantaže estate – the most used rootstocks are 1103 Paulsen, Richter 110, and Ruggeri 140, all considered drought-resistant. In addition, in the private sector, on deeper and more humid soils, Kober 5BB and SO4 are used. Recently, increasing attention has been given to selecting grapevine rootstocks according to local climatic and soil conditions, as well as varietal requirements. At 13. Jul – Plantaže, research on rootstock combination with Vranac is conducted, however focussing on wine quality and not drought resistance.

Changing grape varieties

Another long-term adaptation strategy might be to plant other varieties, such as heat-tolerant, late-ripening varieties, or fungus-tolerant varieties (Santos et al. 2020). 13. Jul – Plantaže owns the national collection of native varieties at Čemovsko field with a size of 0.7ha (Maraš et al. 2020). Furthermore, 100 plants of 7 fungus-tolerant varieties (Bronner, Muscaris, Sauvignier gris, Cabernet Cortis, Prior, Cabernet Cantor, Calardis Blanc) were planted in 2024, as well as 80 plants of 4 rootstocks (Teleki 8B, 420A, Paulsen 1103P, Richter 110) to test them under Montenegrin conditions (Figure 17). Different clones of the Vranac grape variety have also been tested. Herein, the aim is to find later-ripening clones. Research on international varieties is done as well to see how these are performing under Montenegrin conditions.

Figure 17: Grapes of Sauvignier gris

Relocate vineyards

If regions become too warm or dry for sustainable production, it might be reasonable to shift vineyards towards higher altitudes, coastal regions or less exposed sites (Santos et al. 2020). In Montenegro, relocation of vineyards will be considered more intensively in future with accelerating climate change, as winegrowers have the potential to shift vineyards to higher altitudes, for example, in the Nudo Viticultural Region. Moreover, new vineyards are developing in the North of Montenegro with cooler climatic conditions.

Precision Viticulture

Usage of installed sensors or a digital geo-information system (GIS) can help to track and meet, for example, the specific water and nutrient needs in a short time. This allows for efficient water supply management to reduce costs and protect the environment (Stojanović et al. 2021). 13. Jul – Plantaže has experience with precision viticulture (Maraš, Popovic and Pavicevic 2019, Maraš et al. 2020) and is using weather stations as well as GPS mechanisations. DSS can help in more precise pest and disease control to allow farmers to better cope with extreme weather events, having a positive effect on the economy and environment (Marinko et al. 2025).

5.2. MITIGATION MEASURES

A significant share of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions originates from the agriculture, forestry, and other land uses sector, accounting for approximately 22% of total net anthropogenic emissions, equivalent to 13 gigatonnes of CO₂-equivalent. Within this sector, about 50% of emissions are attributed to agricultural activities (IPCC, 2019).

In this context, the wine production supply chain involves a series of agronomic operations that directly affect its overall emissions, with impacts ranging from vineyard management to winery processes. (Longobottom et al., 2015; Ghiglieno et al., 2023). Key operations such as fertilisation, plant protection treatments, irrigation, mechanical activities, and cellar management play a crucial role, as they directly impact the carbon footprint of wine production (Litskas et al. 2020). Thus, implementing appropriate mitigation strategies that enhance carbon sequestration in soil and plants, improve the efficiency of mechanised operations, and optimize inputs use across all stages of wine production can significantly reduce emissions.

Soil management and Carbon stock

Tillage alters the physical and chemical properties of soil, accelerating soil organic matter (SOM) degradation and oxidation. This releases macronutrients but also increases nutrient leaching and GHG emissions (Visconti et al., 2024). Minimum tillage, which involves shallow cultivation (10–15 cm) without inverting soil layers, reduces soil disturbance, slows SOM loss and enhances carbon sequestration while ensuring weed control. It also lowers soil compaction, decreases machinery use, and supports both soil health and biodiversity by preserving arthropod habitats (Jasrotia et al., 2023).

To reduce soil disturbance and mechanical work in vineyard inter-rows, cover crops are an effective soil management strategy. They absorb atmospheric CO₂ through photosynthesis and help form stable soil aggregates, boosting long-term soil carbon storage (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2015). However, choosing the right species is crucial, especially in drought-prone areas like parts of Montenegro, where water availability is limited during key growth periods. In such cases, self-reseeding, low-competitive legumes can be beneficial by fixing nitrogen, improving soil fertility, and limiting competition with grapevines (Abdalla et al., 2019; Silvestroni et al., 2024).

Beyond their direct agronomic benefits, these practices contribute to greater long-term soil stability and enhanced vineyard biodiversity, fostering a more balanced ecosystem. Integrating these approaches into business-as-usual management can help vineyards maintain productivity while progressively reducing intensive soil interventions (e.g., ploughing).

Residue management

The management of pruning residues contributes to GHG emissions due to machinery use for transportation, and CO₂ release from burning (Simoes et al., 2023).

Adopting circular strategies, such as converting residues into wood chips, compost, or biochar, offers a more sustainable alternative, especially when combined with winery by-products. In wine regions like Montenegro, where carbon-rich soil amendments are already in use, integrating biochar into existing practices can further enhance soil carbon storage.

Biochar, in particular, stabilises carbon in the soil and reduces atmospheric losses when enriched with organic matter (Giagnoni et al., 2019; Idbella et al., 2024).

Additionally, biochar influences soil texture characteristics, particularly by reducing bulk density and increasing water availability. This improvement is particularly significant in sandy soils (Fischer et al., 2019). However, achieving a notable increase in water retention requires a high application rate (>20 t/ha), as reported by Omondi et al. (2016) and Baronti et al. (2022).

Thus, biochar emerges as a valuable soil amendment for stabilising soil carbon stocks and, depending on soil characteristics (Razzaghi et al., 2020), can also contribute to enhanced water storage (Figure 18). This, in turn, supports more efficient water use, which is particularly beneficial in regions where precipitation is expected to decline, like Montenegro, reinforcing the role of biochar in sustainable and resilient vineyard management.

Figure 18: Biochar application.

Precision viticulture

Precision viticulture technologies have significant potential for optimising resource use and minimising environmental impacts by enabling targeted application of fertilisers, pesticides, and irrigation based on vineyard-specific needs. Field sensors can monitor key variables such as soil moisture and air and soil temperature, providing real-time data to optimise irrigation scheduling and reduce CO₂ emissions associated with the electricity required for water pumping (Balafoutis et al., 2017).

Data obtained from remote sensing further enhances vineyard monitoring, providing spatial and temporal insights into growth patterns, water and disease incidence based on vegetation spectral reflectance.

In addition, UAVs offer very high-resolution imaging, making them effective tools for early detection of stress conditions in vineyards, such as those caused by flavescence dorée and esca (Albetis et al., 2017; Di Gennaro et al., 2016) (Figure 19). By identifying stress early through multispectral imaging, they allow for targeted treatments, reducing pesticide use, tractor passes, and related CO₂ emissions.

Figure 19: Volume of water for optimisation of pesticide treatments in a vineyard.

Once collected, vineyard data can be used to create georeferenced maps that show spatial variability and support site-specific management. Integrated into DSS, these maps, such as vigour maps, help detect canopy stress (e.g., water shortage or disease), enabling precise input application and improving efficiency when used with GPS-guided tractors (Ammoniacci et al., 2021; Padua et al., 2019).

In Montenegro, precision viticulture is seen as a sustainable strategy to reduce emissions, but limited adoption highlights the need for training programs to improve technical skills and promote its use.

Energy efficiency strategies in the winery

Winery operations contribute significantly to emissions, with cooling systems accounting for much of the energy use during vinification. These systems are essential for wine quality and stability, but improving their efficiency can reduce both environmental impact and costs. The most energy-intensive stages include grape reception, fermentation, tartaric stabilisation, and ageing.

Grape cooling at reception is among the most energy-intensive steps due to the sharp temperature difference between the field and cellar. Structural solutions like thermal insulation and underground cellars can cut energy use by up to 63% (Benni et al., 2013), while insulated storage tanks (e.g. using polyurethane or ceramic coatings) further improve efficiency (Malvoni et al., 2017). Beyond structural improvements, monitoring energy consumption helps to identify inefficient machinery, allowing for timely maintenance or replacement. Shifting high-energy operations outside of peak hours (9:00 AM - 5:00 PM) to early mornings or nighttime can further optimise energy demand and costs (Cottes et al., 2020). Finally, photovoltaic systems present a sustainable energy solution in the long term, especially in regions with high solar potential (Figures 20, 21). Although initial investment costs are substantial, financial incentives such as feed-in tariffs can support the transition, making renewable energy adoption a viable strategy for wineries.

Figure 20: Agrovoltaic system.

Figure 21: Research on viti-voltaic systems at WBI Freiburg in Germany.

5.3 CASE STUDIES IN MONTENEGRO

As part of the MONTEVITIS project, four partner wineries, BUK, Vučinić, Kruna, and Rajković, participated in pilot case studies aimed at demonstrating how digital tools and climate data services can support more adaptive vineyard management in Montenegro. Located primarily in the Lake Skadar basin, these wineries represent a diverse cross-section of vineyard environments and production approaches. Environmental sensors were installed across selected plots to monitor key parameters such as air temperature, humidity, solar radiation, and soil moisture. This data was fed into the MONTEVITIS DSS, enabling producers to visualise local microclimatic dynamics and better understand site-specific vulnerabilities to climate stress.

In addition to environmental monitoring, a mobile-friendly web application to facilitate the structured collection of phenological data directly from the field. Vineyard managers and staff were able to log key phenophases, such as budburst, flowering, veraison, and harvest, using a standardised protocol aligned with BBCH scale terminology. This contributed to the development of a shared, geo-referenced dataset that links phenological trends with both observed weather conditions and climate projections. The application not only improved data consistency across different producers but also helped raise awareness about the timing shifts already taking place due to climate change.

The case studies provided a practical testing ground for integrating monitoring, modelling, and producer experience. While not focused on agronomic interventions, the pilots demonstrated the value of precise, site-specific data in supporting risk assessment and decision-making. Differences observed between vineyard plots, sometimes even within the same microregion, reinforced the need for localised adaptation strategies. Feedback from partner wineries also informed refinements to the DSS and confirmed the usability of digital tools in real-world vineyard operations, paving the way for wider adoption in the Montenegrin wine sector.

In addition to the MONTEVITIS pilots, a case study was also conducted as part of the EU-funded H2020 DEMETER project, which focused on the implementation of smart farming technologies in various agricultural sectors across Europe. Within this project, a comprehensive digital infrastructure was established at one of the largest wine producers in Southeast Europe. Equipment installed included a meteorological station, multiple soil moisture sensors, pest monitoring traps, and a LoRa gateway for real-time data transmission. Besides this, the winery 13. Jul - Plantaže was also selected to test the IoT-connected atomiser, H3O system (Healthy crop, Healthy environment, Healthy finances) developed by the Spanish company Pulverizadores Fede, which was provided free of charge for the duration of the pilot. This IoT-connected atomiser enables direct communication between agronomists and tractor operators, allowing remote configuration of spray operations based on current field conditions. The system records detailed data on each treatment and uploads it to a central platform, ensuring traceability, reduced chemical use, and improved treatment precision. Field trials demonstrated up to 25% reduction in pesticide use, 48% decrease in spray drift, and 4 litres/hour fuel savings. These results highlight the potential of smart machinery and decision support tools to enhance sustainability, efficiency, and product safety in viticulture.

Furthermore, within the TRACEWINDU project, funded by the HORIZON 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie RISE programme, a research and innovation exchange initiative was launched to enhance traceability and authenticity in the wine industry. The project brings together academic and industry partners from Spain, Italy, France, Montenegro, Serbia, and Argentina, aiming to foster sustainable grape and wine production and promote international knowledge exchange.

The TRACEWINDU case study focused on the development of smart-label technologies, QR code-based dynamic labels integrated with blockchain technology, to ensure complete transparency and traceability throughout the wine value chain. These digital labels provide consumers with detailed information about the product's origin, vineyard practices, grape treatment methods, organoleptic properties, and potential health-related components. Additionally, the project explored the use of advanced plant protection strategies and tools for verifying the geographic origin and quality of wine. These plant protection products are environmentally friendly alternatives, which could contribute to a reduction in pesticide use and promote more sustainable viticulture practices. For producers, this represents an innovative approach to digital product certification, consumer engagement, and alignment with future EU regulatory standards on digital labelling. Moreover, such practices support broader goals of climate change mitigation through reduced chemical inputs and improved ecosystem health.

A case study was also implemented through the irrigNET pilot project, focusing on precise viticulture and smart irrigation. The initiative was carried out in collaboration between 13. Jul - Plantaže, DunavNet (Novi Sad), and the Faculty of Information Systems and Technologies at the University of Donja Gorica. The primary objective was to optimise irrigation practices in vineyards by deploying soil moisture monitoring sensors at various depths. These sensors provided real-time data on soil moisture dynamics, helping vineyard managers determine the precise timing and quantity of irrigation needed. The system was supported by a mobile and web application, allowing easy access to the data and enabling more informed, site-specific decisions. By avoiding over-irrigation and maintaining optimal soil moisture levels, the project not only contributed to cost savings and water efficiency but also helped preserve grape quality, which is essential for premium wine production. The irrigNET case demonstrated how low-cost digital solutions can play a vital role in sustainable vineyard management and support the broader shift toward climate-resilient agriculture.

6

Future perspectives for viticulture in Montenegro: knowledge gaps and future challenges

Future perspectives for viticulture in Montenegro: knowledge gaps and future challenges

SUMMARY

Looking ahead, the future of viticulture in Montenegro will depend on its capacity to anticipate change, close knowledge gaps, and strengthen collaboration across the sector. Climate-driven shifts in suitability, water availability, and pest dynamics require forward-looking strategies supported by robust data, research, and innovation. Building long-term networks for data sharing, enhancing research and analytical capacities, and investing in targeted training are essential steps toward this transition. At the same time, stronger linkages between winegrowers, research institutions, and policymakers can accelerate the uptake of climate-smart practices and digital tools. By embedding innovation within a collaborative and knowledge-based framework, Montenegrin viticulture can move toward a more resilient, competitive, and sustainable future.

6.1 NEW PERSPECTIVE IN VITICULTURE IN MONTENEGRO: MAIN RESEARCH FINDINGS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The MONTEVITIS project has revealed several critical insights that shape a new perspective on the future of viticulture in Montenegro. One of the most notable findings is the confirmation of significant climate shifts, particularly in the Lake Skadar basin, where grape-growing conditions are being rapidly altered by increased temperatures, prolonged droughts, and extreme weather events such as hailstorms and heatwaves. Bioclimatic indices such as the Winkler Index and Growing Season Average Temperature (GST) show that large areas of Montenegro are already approaching or exceeding the upper thermal thresholds suitable for high-quality wine production. These changes have major implications for grapevine development, yield, and quality, especially for native varieties like Vranac that are closely tied to local terroirs. Taken together, these findings point to the need for a strategic transition from traditional practices to more resilient, data-informed approaches to vineyard management.

One of the key contributions of the project has been the development of a data-driven foundation for more resilient vineyard planning and management. This includes the creation of a digital DSS that integrates vineyard sensor data, phenological observations, and climate projections. In parallel, MONTEVITIS applied predictive modelling approaches to assess future bioclimatic suitability of wine-growing zones and the expected shifts in key viticultural indicators under different climate scenarios. These tools offer stakeholders, particularly small and medium producers, improved capacity to anticipate and respond to climate risks with site-specific insights.

Looking ahead, the findings suggest that a transition toward more adaptive viticulture practices is necessary and increasingly urgent. While MONTEVITIS did not test specific interventions such as drought-tolerant rootstocks or canopy modifications, the predictive modelling and monitoring systems developed through the project provide the analytical foundation to evaluate such options in the future. Further research is needed to characterise the resilience of native grape varieties and to refine agro-climatic zoning for future vineyard planning. By establishing a robust digital infrastructure and promoting knowledge exchange, MONTEVITIS has opened new avenues for climate-smart viticulture in Montenegro, grounded in data, collaboration, and local specificity. In addition, investment in R&D, upskilling winegrowers, and fostering public-private partnerships will ensure that the sector not only adapts to climate change but thrives through innovation and sustainability.

To fully capitalise on these findings, it is recommended to establish follow-up initiatives focusing on:

- 1 Pilot testing of climate-resilient grape varieties and rootstocks and canopy management techniques;
- 2 Development of training modules and capacity building programs in precision viticulture and adaptation measures to climate change;
- 3 Gradual expansion of the DSS platform to additional vineyard zones and stakeholders.

After all, there is both a need and an opportunity to establish a permanent multi-stakeholder platform for knowledge exchange, bringing together researchers, producers, public institutions, and private technology providers. Such a platform would further enhance long-term impact. Additionally, sustained investment in R&D, upskilling of winegrowers, and the fostering of public-private partnerships will be essential to ensure that the sector not only adapts to climate change but also thrives through innovation, collaboration, and sustainability.

6.2 STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION: LONG-TERM NETWORKS FOR DATA SHARING

Sustainable development of the viticulture sector in Montenegro requires enhanced collaboration between key stakeholders, including wine producers, researchers, policymakers, and industry professionals. Establishing long-term networks that facilitate data sharing and capacity-building initiatives is crucial for strengthening resilience to climate change, improving production quality, and promoting sustainable viticulture practices. Despite Montenegro's growing viticulture sector, one of the key challenges remains the fragmented nature of knowledge exchange and the limited integration of technological advancements in vineyard management. Addressing these gaps requires a structured approach that ensures continuous cooperation and knowledge transfer among stakeholders. Furthermore, bridging the gap between data availability and field-level decision-making requires continuous education, advisory services, and hands-on training for producers.

Existing national organisations, such as the National Association of Winegrowers and Winemakers of Montenegro and the National Association of Sommeliers of Montenegro, play a crucial role in connecting winegrowers, promoting education, and fostering the exchange of best practices. However, more structured mechanisms are needed to integrate real-time vineyard data with decision-making processes, particularly in response to climate variability, such as standardised data-sharing protocols, inter-institutional working groups, and digital dashboards for operational planning. The introduction of a DSS as part of Montenegro's viticultural framework facilitates a centralised system for collecting, processing, and disseminating key vineyard data. By leveraging IoT sensors, climate projections, and phenological data, the DSS supports improved collaboration between researchers and vineyard managers, ensuring the direct application of data-driven insights to vineyard operations. This structured data-sharing approach allows for more precise decision-making in vineyard management, including irrigation planning, disease control, and yield optimisation.

6.3 CAPACITY-BUILDING INITIATIVES

Capacity-building initiatives must focus on training programs, workshops, and knowledge-exchange platforms that empower winegrowers to adopt modern viticulture techniques. These initiatives should be designed in collaboration with universities, research institutions, and international partners to ensure alignment with global best practices. In particular, programs should address digital literacy, the application of precision viticulture tools, climate risk awareness, and sustainable resource management. Special attention should be given to empowering young professionals and women entrepreneurs in viticulture, fostering inclusive growth and generational renewal in rural areas.

Strengthening research collaboration through joint projects, participation in European Union research initiatives, and engagement with regional networks will enhance the technical competencies of Montenegrin wine producers while fostering innovation. Establishing mentorship programs where experienced winemakers support emerging producers can further solidify long-term knowledge transfer and sectoral growth. Additionally, introducing standardised training modules and certification schemes aligned with EU sustainability frameworks (such as Farm to Fork or Organic Transition) will help producers meet export requirements and strengthen consumer confidence.

The successful implementation of a sustainable viticulture strategy in Montenegro depends on strengthening these collaborative networks. A well-integrated stakeholder ecosystem that encourages open data exchange, continuous education, and adaptive decision-making will enable the viticulture sector to navigate future challenges effectively. By institutionalising collaboration through formalised data-sharing agreements, capacity-building programs, and stakeholder engagement strategies, Montenegro can position itself as a leader in climate-smart viticulture, ensuring the long-term sustainability and competitiveness of its wine industry in the international market.

7

Digital atlas

Digital atlas

As Montenegro's wine sector faces increasing pressure from climate change, market dynamics, and the need for sustainable production, having accurate, real-time data on vineyard conditions is becoming essential. The Digital Atlas of Winegrowers in Montenegro represents an advanced geospatial platform designed to provide an interactive and data-driven representation of the country's viticulture landscape, as represented in [Figure 22](#). The atlas integrates critical data on vineyard locations, grape varieties, soil characteristics, production metrics, and climate conditions. By leveraging geospatial technologies and real-time data collection, the Digital Atlas serves as a centralised resource for wine producers, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders involved in viticulture and agricultural planning. It will be an integral part of the MONTEVITIS DSS, ensuring that stakeholders have seamless access to relevant data for optimising vineyard management and climate adaptation strategies.

Figure 22: Digital atlas of Montenegro as an integral part of Montevitis DSS.

The Digital Atlas operates as a GIS-based mapping system, offering a structured and user-friendly interface for accessing detailed vineyard information. Each vineyard is geo-referenced and linked to a comprehensive database containing attributes such as cultivated grape varieties, surface area, soil classification, production capacity, and agronomic practices. The platform integrates climate and environmental data, incorporating temperature patterns, precipitation trends, humidity levels, and extreme weather event tracking to support vineyard management and adaptation strategies. Real-time monitoring and data collection are facilitated through IoT sensors, meteorological stations, and remote sensing technologies, ensuring up-to-date environmental parameters and soil conditions.

As a core component of the DSS, the Digital Atlas is being developed to support data-driven vineyard management. Its long-term vision is to integrate advanced decision-support tools such as irrigation planning, disease monitoring, and harvest optimisation. The platform is designed to combine information from various sources, including vineyard registries, satellite imagery and remote sensing, meteorological networks, and soil databases. At this stage, some of these data layers and functionalities have already been implemented, providing a practical foundation while allowing for further expansion in the future.

The Digital Atlas offers various applications across different stakeholders. Winegrowers will benefit from optimised vineyard management through access to site-specific agronomic and climatic data. Researchers will have enhanced capabilities for studying climate impacts on viticulture and evaluating adaptation measures. Policymakers will be able to leverage data-driven support for sustainable agricultural planning and decision-making. The wine industry will gain improved visibility of Montenegro's wine production landscape, facilitating market analysis and promotional efforts.

Future developments for the Digital Atlas include the expansion of sensor networks to improve real-time data accuracy, integration of AI-powered analytics for predictive modelling and adaptive vineyard management, blockchain-based traceability features for enhanced transparency and authentication in wine production, and stakeholder engagement initiatives to encourage crowdsourced data contributions for improved dataset accuracy and completeness.

8

Conclusions

Conclusions

CLIMATE CHANGE POSES A PROFOUND AND ESCALATING THREAT TO MONTENEGRIN VITICULTURE, WITH THE MOST UNSETTLING IMPACTS CONCENTRATED IN THE BASIN OF LAKE SKADAR, THE COUNTRY'S MOST PRODUCTIVE WINE REGION, HOME TO OVER 99% OF VINEYARD SURFACES.

Projections indicate a rise in growing season temperatures by up to 6.4°C by the end of the century, accompanied by prolonged droughts, reduced precipitation, and a dramatic increase in hot days and tropical nights. These climatic shifts are expected to shorten the ripening phase, diminish wine quality, and increase the frequency of stress events such as sunburn, drought, and hailstorms. Additionally, the phenological cycle of grapevines is changing, leading to earlier budburst, flowering, and harvest, and thereby increasing vulnerability to both spring frosts and summer heat extremes. Without timely and localised adaptation measures, the sustainability and competitiveness of Montenegro's wine sector will be severely threatened.

In response to these challenges, the MONTEVITIS project has delivered a robust set of adaptation and mitigation tools aimed at improving the sector's climate resilience.

Precision viticulture technologies, including a DSS, real-time microclimate monitoring, and phenological tracking, have been introduced to support more informed and site-specific decision-making. These tools have enabled producers to visualise local microclimatic dynamics, anticipate risks, and tailor interventions at the vineyard level. Adaptation strategies already tested include improved irrigation scheduling, the use of drought- and heat-tolerant rootstocks and clones, adjusted canopy and row orientation, and selective shading techniques. On the mitigation side, practices such as reduced tillage, biochar application, and energy optimisation have been explored to reduce the sector's carbon footprint.

The Skadar basin has emerged as the most vulnerable zone, with multiple areas nearing or surpassing optimal thermal thresholds for quality wine production.

Case studies conducted within MONTEVITIS, revealed high spatial variability between vineyard plots, even within the same microregion, underscoring the importance of localised strategies that reflect specific vineyard conditions.

Phenological monitoring through a mobile-friendly application allowed producers to log budburst, flowering, veraison, and harvest in a standardised and geo-referenced way, enabling more accurate alignment between vineyard management and climatic conditions. These interventions not only improved the accuracy of data collection but also raised awareness among growers about the timing shifts already taking place.

To ensure long-term sustainability, Montenegro must continue to invest in digital tools, data infrastructure, and capacity building. One of the key lessons of MONTEVITIS is the importance of institutionalising cooperation between researchers, producers, policymakers, and the private sector. A more structured ecosystem for data sharing, real-time analytics, and knowledge transfer will be essential in responding to future climatic extremes. At the same time, the sector must scale up the adoption of sustainable practices, such as reduced pesticide use and renewable energy integration, not only to mitigate environmental impact but to meet future EU regulatory standards and market expectations.

By proactively responding to climate challenges and embracing digital transformation, Montenegro is well-positioned to emerge as a regional leader in climate-smart viticulture.

MONTEVITIS has laid the foundation for this future, but continued effort is needed to expand its reach, engage more producers, and formalise long-term support mechanisms. The development of a unified Digital Atlas and DSS, alongside real-time environmental monitoring and applied research, provides a replicable model for data-informed decision-making. To build on this momentum, coordinated national efforts backed by sustained R&D investment, targeted training, and multistakeholder collaboration are necessary.

Ultimately, the transition to resilient, adaptive viticulture will depend not only on innovation but on inclusion. By strengthening local knowledge systems, empowering growers through accessible technology, and fostering a culture of shared responsibility, Montenegro can ensure that its wine sector not only survives the pressures of climate change but thrives, preserving both its heritage and its future.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdalla, M., Hastings, A., Cheng, K., Yue, Q., Chadwick, D., Espenberg, M., Truu, J., Rees, R. M., & Smith, P. (2019). A critical review of the impacts of cover crops on nitrogen leaching, net greenhouse gas balance and crop productivity. *Global Change Biology*, 25(8), 2530–2543.
- Albetis, J., Duthoit, S., Guttler, F., Jacquin, A., Goulard, M., Poilvé, H., Féret, J.-B., & Dedieu, G. (2017). Detection of Flavescence dorée grapevine disease using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) multispectral imagery. *Remote Sensing*, 9(4), 308.
- Ammoniaci, M., Kartsiotis, S.-P., Perria, R., & Storchi, P. (2021). State of the art of monitoring technologies and data processing for precision viticulture. *Agriculture*, 11(3), 201.
- Bakic, I., Radonjić, S., Mirović, V., Peruničić, M., Atak, A., Radović, A., & Čolić, S. (2025). Impact of foliar nanocalcium fertilization on yield and wine characteristics of Vranac wine grapes. *Advanced Technologies*, 14(1).
- Balafoutis, A. T., Koundouras, S., Anastasiou, E., Fountas, S., & Arvanitis, K. (2017). Life cycle assessment of two vineyards after the application of precision viticulture techniques: A case study. *Sustainability*, 9(11), 1997.
- Baronti, S., Magno, R., Maienza, A., Montagnoli, A., Ungaro, F., & Vaccari, F. P. (2022). Long-term effect of biochar on soil-plant water relations and fine roots: Results after 10 years of a vineyard experiment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 851, 158225.
- Blanco-Canqui, H., Shaver, T. M., Lindquist, J. L., Shapiro, C. A., Elmore, R. W., Francis, C. A., & Hergert, G. W. (2015). Cover crops and ecosystem services: Insights from studies in temperate soils. *Agronomy Journal*, 107(6), 2449–2474.
- Di Gennaro, S. F., Battiston, E., Di Marco, S., Facini, O., Matese, A., Nocentini, M., Palliotti, A., & Mugnai, L. (2016). UAV-based remote sensing to monitor grapevine leaf stripe disease within a vineyard affected by esca complex. *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, 55(2), 262–275.
- Fernandes, A., Kovač, N., Fraga, H., Fonseca, A., Šučur Radonjić, S., Simeunović, M., Ratković, K., Menz, C., Costafreda-Aumedes, S., & Santos, J. A. (2024). Challenges to viticulture in Montenegro under climate change. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 13(8), 270.
- Fraga, H., Freitas, T. R., Fonseca, A., Fernandes, A., & Santos, J. A. (2024). Climate change implications on the viticulture geography. In P. Martins-Lopes (Ed.), *Advances in Botanical Research* (Vol. 110, pp. 27–69). Academic Press.
- Ghiglieno, I., Simonetto, A., Facciano, L., Tonni, M., Donna, P., Valenti, L., & Gilioli, G. (2023). Comparing the carbon footprint of conventional and organic vineyards in Northern Italy. *Sustainability*, 15(6), 5252.
- Giagnoni, L., Maienza, A., Baronti, S., Vaccari, F. P., Genesio, L., Taiti, C., Martellini, T., Scodellini, R., Cincinelli, A., Costa, C., Mancuso, S., & Renella, G. (2019). Long-term soil biological fertility, volatile organic compounds and chemical properties in a vineyard soil after biochar amendment. *Geoderma*, 344, 127–136.
- Hargreaves, G. H., & Zohrab, A. S. (1985). Crop evapotranspiration from temperature. *Applied Engineering in Agriculture*, 1(2), 96–99.
- Hunter, J. J., Volschenk, C. G., & Booyse, M. (2017). Vineyard row orientation and grape ripeness level effects on vegetative and reproductive growth characteristics of *Vitis vinifera* L. cv. Shiraz/101-14 Mgt. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 84, 47–57.
- Idbella, M., Baronti, S., Giagnoni, L., Renella, G., Becagli, M., Cardelli, R., Maienza, A., Vaccari, F. P., & Bonanomi, G. (2024). Long-term effects of biochar on soil chemistry, biochemistry, and microbiota: Results from a 10-year field vineyard experiment. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 195, 105217.
- Jones, G. V. (2018). The climate component of terroir. *Elements*, 14(3), 167–172.
- Jones, G. V., Snead, N., & Nelson, P. (2010). Spatial analysis of climate in winegrape growing regions in the western United States. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture*, 61(3), 313–326.
- Karger, D. N., Conrad, O., Böhner, J., Kawohl, T., Kreft, H., Soria-Auza, R. W., Zimmermann, N. E., Linder, H. P., & Kessler, M. (2017). Climatologies at high resolution for the Earth's land surface areas. *Scientific Data*, 4, 170122.

Leolini, L., Bregaglio, S., Moriondo, M., Ramos, M.C., Bindi, M., Ginaldi, F., 2018. A model library to simulate grapevine growth and development: software implementation, sensitivity analysis and field level application. *European Journal of Agronomy* 99, 92–105.

Leolini, L., Bregaglio, S., Ginaldi, F., Costafreda-Aumedes, S., Di Gennaro, S.F., Matese, A., Maselli, F., Caruso, G., Palai, G., Bajocco, S., Bindi, M., Moriondo, M., 2023. Use of remote sensing-derived fPAR data in a grapevine simulation model for estimating vine biomass accumulation and yield variability at sub-field level. *Precision Agric* 24, 705–726.

Maras, V., Kodžulović, V., Raičević, J., Gazivoda, A., & Perišić, M. (2016). Influence of different rootstocks on grape and wine quality of Montenegrin autochthonous grapevine cultivar 'Vranac'. In F. Gaiotti, F. Battista, & D. Tomasi (Eds.), *International Symposium on Grapevine Roots* (Vol. 1136, pp. 45–49). International Society for Horticultural Science.

Maras, V., Popović, T., Gajinov, S., Mugoša, M., Popović, V., Savović, A., Pavičević, K., & Mirović, V. (2019). Optimal irrigation as a tool of precision agriculture. In L. Joźwiak et al. (Eds.), *2019 8th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)* (pp. 533–536). IEEE.

Maras, V., Popović, T., Gajinov, S., Mugoša, M., Popović, V., Savović, A., Pavičević, K., & Mirović, V. (2020). Precision viticulture using wireless sensor networks. In R. Stojanović et al. (Eds.), *2020 9th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)* (pp. 202–207). IEEE.

Marinko, J., Kuzmanovski, V., Ramsden, M., & Debeljak, M. (2025). Overcoming barriers to the adoption of decision support systems in integrated pest management in some European countries. *Agronomy*, 15(2).

Minnaar, P., van der Rijst, M., & Hunter, J. J. (2022). Grapevine row orientation, vintage and grape ripeness effect on phenolic composition of Syrah grapes. *OENO One*, 56(1), Article 1.

Molitor, D., Heilemann, K., Jiménez-Rodríguez, C. D., Hüther, S., Trapp, O., Stalport, A., ... Junk, J. (2025). UniPhen "PIWI": High-resolution simulation of the phenological development of fungus-tolerant cultivars. *OENO One*, 59(2), Article 2.

Pallotti, L., Dottori, E., Lattanzi, T., Lanari, V., Brillante, L., & Silvestroni, O. (2025). Anti-hail shading nets and kaolin application: Protecting grape production to ensure grape quality in Mediterranean vineyards. *Horticulturae*, 11(2), 110.

Pallotti, L., Silvestroni, O., Dottori, E., Lattanzi, T., & Lanari, V. (2023). Effects of shading nets as a form of adaptation to climate change on grape production: A review. *OENO One*, 57(2), Article 2.

Santos, J. A., Fraga, H., Malheiro, A. C., Moutinho-Pereira, J., Dinis, L. T., Correia, C., Moriondo, M., Leolini, L., Dibari, C., Costafreda-Aumedes, S., Kartschall, T., Menz, C., Molitor, D., Junk, J., Beyer, M., & Schultz, H. R. (2020). A review of the potential climate change impacts and adaptation options for European viticulture. *Applied Sciences*, 10(9), 3092.

chultz, H. R., & Jones, G. V. (2010). Climate-induced historic and future changes in viticulture. *Journal of Wine Research*, 21(2–3), 137–145.

Simões, C. L., Simões, R., Gonçalves, A. S., & Nunes, L. J. R. (2023). Environmental analysis of the valorization of woody biomass residues: A comparative study with vine pruning leftovers in Portugal. *Sustainability*, 15(20), 14950.

Simeunović, M.; Ratković, K.; Kovač, N.; Racković, T.; Fernandes, A. A Knowledge-Driven Framework for a Decision Support Platform in Sustainable Viticulture: Integrating Climate Data and Supporting Stakeholder Collaboration. *Sustainability* 2025, 17, 1387.

Stojanović, R., Maraš, V., Radonjić, S., Martić, A., Đurković, J., Pavičević, K., Mirović, V., & Cvetković, M. (2021). A feasible IoT-based system for precision agriculture. In *2021 10th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)* (pp. 1–4). IEEE.

Tscholl, S., Candiago, S., Marsoner, T., Fraga, H., Giupponi, C., & Egarter Vigl, L. (2024). Climate resilience of European wine regions. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 6254.

van Leeuwen, C., Sgubin, G., Bois, B., et al. (2024). Climate change impacts and adaptations of wine production. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 5, 258–275.

Visconti, F., López, R., & Olego, M. Á. (2024). The health of vineyard soils: Towards a sustainable viticulture. *Horticulturae*, 10(2), 154.

Winkler, A. J., Cook, J. A., Kliewer, W. M., & Lider, L. A. (1974). *General viticulture*. University of California Press.

www.montevitis.eu

[@MontevitisProject](https://www.youtube.com/@MontevitisProject)

[montevitis-he](https://www.linkedin.com/company/montevitis-he)

[montevitis](https://twitter.com/montevitis)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Coordination and Support action under the Grant Agreement n° 101059461.